

ASSESSMENT OF POST HARVEST LOSSES OF MANGO FRUITS AND ASSOCIATED CHALLENGES IN BAUCHI STATE NIGERIA

S. H. KARI¹, A. TIJANI², M. U. SABO³, & P. O. UNAH⁴

^{1, 2, 3, & 4}Department of Crop Production, Faculty of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi, Nigeria

Corresponding Author: shehuhadukari@gmail.com, +2348065060610

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14839098>

ABSTRACT

The study investigates the assessment of post-harvest losses of mango fruits and associated challenges in Bauchi state, Nigeria. Mango production plays a vital role in the agricultural sector, yet post-harvest losses persist. A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted to assess post-harvest handling practices and their impact on spoilage. Data were collected through structured questionnaires administered to mango farmers. The questionnaire demonstrated validity through expert review and reliability through pilot testing. Data analysis involved descriptive statistics. Demographic analysis highlighted the characteristics of mango fruit farmers in Bauchi state. The majority of the sample population was Male (73.31%), with individuals aged 41-50 representing the largest age group (48.31%). Many had never been to school, and hire labour are the primary sources of employment (76.7%). The findings reflected critical insights into the factors contributing to post-harvest losses. Transportation, packaging, decay, and poor grading were identified as significant contributors to mango fruit losses. Specifically, transportation accounted for a spoilage proportion of 35% at 40% transportation time. Similarly, packaging contributed to a spoilage proportion of 36% at 40% reliance on packaging. Decay and poor grading also played significant roles with spoilage proportions of 33.3%. Observed decay and poor grading accounted for 20% each. The findings of the study shed light on the demographic characteristics and post-harvest handling practices of mango farmers in Bauchi state, Nigeria. Strategies aimed at enhancing transportation efficiency, optimizing packaging methods, managing decay effectively, and improving grading standards could significantly mitigate post-harvest losses and enhance the economic viability of mango production in the region.

Keywords: Post-Harvest Losses, Mango Fruits, Assessment, Challenges

INTRODUCTION

Mango (*Mangifera Indica L.*) is an important tropical fruit crop in Nigeria, and its production has a long history in the country. The history of mango (*Mangifera Indica L.*) production in Nigeria dates back to the 15th century, when Portuguese explorers introduced the first mango tree to the country, laying the foundation for the crop's significance in Nigeria's tropical fruits production (Adegbite, *et al.*, 2018). The fruits are widely grown in the southern and middle belt region of the country where the climate is suitable for its cultivation. Over the years, mango production in Nigeria has increased significantly due to the high demand for the fruit both domestically and for export. The Nigerian government has implemented several policies and programs to support the growth of the mango industries, such as the National Horticultural Research Institute (NIHORT) (Adeyemo, *et al.*, 2019). This initiative has helped to increase productivity and reduce postharvest losses, resulting in

increased revenue for farmers and the country as a whole. The economic value of fresh mango fruits to most household especially in the rural areas of Nigeria cannot be overestimated as most families depend greatly on the income they make from mango for their livelihood (Onyeani, *et al.*, 2012).

Mango fruit is a good source of polyphenols, ascorbic acid, carotenoids, vitamin and carbohydrates (Singh, *et al.*, 2013). The nutritional properties of mango, especially antioxidants, are essential for human health as they known to boost the immune system and also prevent cardiovascular diseases and various types of cancers (Muhammad *et al.*, 2014). The fruit is susceptible to various postharvest diseases such as anthracnose, and physiological disorder including chilling, injury, spongy tissue and lenticel sport, unfortunately, those individual problems or their combination may result in postharvest losses as well as loss of revenue for the producers and everyone involved in the postharvest value chain. A significant proportion of losses of mango occur during storage and transportation as a result of poor handling and improper facilities (Sivakumar, *et al.*, 2011).

There is no mango variety or cultivars include those found in Nigeria that has been documented to be completely resistance, to fungal rot diseases (Tarnowski & Ploetz, 2008; Pondey *et al.*, 2012). There are number of fungi that attack mango fruit at maturity after removal from the tree. Those fungi cause infection during storage and transit, and losses, sustained due to fungal infection during those periods are quite heavy. Fruit losses after harvest are also expected to be high due to poor transportation, handling practice and extended storage period (Chala, *et al.*, 2014).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Post -harvest losses of mango fruit in Bauchi state, Nigeria are excavated by inadequate storage facilities, poor transportation infrastructure, poor grading, poor packaging materials and market inefficiency. Those challenges result in significant economic losses for farmers and hinder access to nitrous fruits for consumers. Understanding those issues is crucial for developing effective intervention to minimize post-harvest losses and improve the mango value chain in the state.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The study aims to investigate the post-harvest losses of Mango fruit and associated challenges in Bauchi State, Nigeria. In order to:

1. Identify the socio-economic characteristics of Mango farmers in the study area.
2. Determine the primary factors contributing to post-harvest losses of mango fruits in the study area.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions are pertinent in this study:

1. What are the socio-economic characteristics of mango farmers in the study area?
2. What are the primary factors contributing to post-harvest losses of mango fruits in the study area?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of Postharvest Losses

Post- harvest losses refer to the reduction in both quantity and quality of food products that occur between harvest and consumption. Quality spoilage includes those that affect the nutrient and caloric composition, acceptability, and edibility of a product are crucial factors in post-harvest losses (Kader, 2002). Quantity spoilage refers to the loss of product amount,

commonly occurring in developing countries (Kitinoja & Gorny, 2010). Post-harvest losses in mangoes are influenced by various factors, including losses due to physical, physiological, mechanical and hygienic conditions (Hayatu & Sani, 2000). Mangoes have high metabolic activities and a short shelf life, resulting in substantial losses between harvesting and consumption (Hayaty & Sani, 2000). Physical handling significance affects post-harvest quality and shelf life (Arah et al, 2015). Proper post-harvest handling practices including harvesting, pre-cooling, cleaning, sorting, transportation, and storage, are essential to maintain quality and extent shelf life (Beckles et al., 2012). Harvesting at the appropriate physiological maturity stage is critical for optimal post-harvest quality (Beckles et al., 2012). Cleaning and disinfecting are crucial for maintaining proper hygiene (FAO, 2008).

Harvest diseases and food-borne illnesses, such as salmonella, cryptosporidium, cyclospora, and Hepatitis A virus, can be transmitted to consumers through fresh fruit and vegetables (Government of India report). Unfortunately, cleaning or disinfecting mangoes after harvest is not a common practice among mango handlers in developing countries, particularly in Africa, due to limited access to portable water or lack of knowledge (Genanew et al, 2013).

Sorting and grading are crucial processes in packaging and marketing fruit and vegetables (Arjanaki, 2013). Sorting removes rotten, damaged, or diseased fruits, which can produce excessive ethylene and affect adjacent fruits (Saltveit et al, 1999). Grading categories fruits and vegetable based on colour, size, and maturity or ripening stage. These processes maintain post-harvest shelf life and quality by limiting the spread of infectious micro-organisms and enabling easy handling (Arjaniji, 2013).

Packaging is essential in protecting food production from mechanical injuries, tampering; add contamination (Prasad & Kochhar, 2014). It involves enclosing the products in a sizeable portion for easy handling. However, using appropriate packaging materials and technique is vital to ensure effective protection and maintenance of post-harvest quality. Unsuitable packaging can cause fruit damage, leading to significant losses (Idah et al., 2007). In many developing countries, common packaging materials used for fruit and vegetables include wooden crates, cardboard boxes, woven palm baskets, paper bags (Food and Agriculture organization, 2014). However, these materials often have limitations, such as being prone to damage, providing inadequate ventilation, or failing to protect against moisture and contamination (Arah et al., 2015). The use of appropriate packaging materials and techniques is crucial to maintain post-harvest quality and reduces losses (Prasad & Kochhar, 2014). Suitable packaging materials should provide adequate protection, ventilation and moisture control as well as be durable, affordable, and environmentally-friendly (Idah et al., 2007).

Post-harvest Diseases of Mango Fruit and Their Control Measures

Mango fruits are susceptible to post harvest diseases, which significantly impair fruit quality and result in substantial losses. Wounds on mango fruits provide entry points for pathogens, leading infections that cause *anthracnose* (*Colletotrichum gloeosporioides*), *Alternaria* black spot (*alternaria alternata*), and stem end rot (*lasiodiplodia theobromae*). To maintain the quality during the supply chain, a combination of pre- and postharvest approach is essential. Those include: orchard hygiene management, fungicide application, heat treatments and temperature management during storage and shipping (Sivakumar et al, 2011; Singh & Zaharah, 2015). While prochloraz fungicide has been widely used for postharvest diseases control in mangoes (Sivakumar et al, 2011), the growing demand for organic and eco-friendly fresh produce has led to the exploration and alternative methods. Hot water treatment (46.1 °C for 75 mins), followed by controlled atmosphere storage (CA) of 3% O₂ + 10% CO₂ has been shown to delay the development of *anthracnose* (Kim et al, 2007; Sigh & Zaharah, 2007).

Post-Harvest Pests of Mango Fruit and Disinfection Treatments

Mangoes are preferred host for various fruit fly species including the Mediterranean fruit fly (*Ceratitis Capitata*), Mexican fruit fly (*Anastrepha SPP*), and Queensland fruit fly (*Bactrocera tryoni*), which are deemed a significant quarantine risk in numerous importing countries (Jacobi et al, 2001). Insecticidal controlled atmosphere (ICA) have shown promise in controlling tephritid fruit fly species, but as a standalone treatment and in combination with other methods (Singh et al, 2013).

METHODOLOGY

The study adopts descriptive cross-sectional approach to asses post-harvest losses of Mango fruit in Bauchi state Nigeria. The population of the study comprises 2642 stake holders involved in the mango fruit supply chain. A multi stage sampling techniques are employed, stratifying region, selecting district and villages within each region, and utilizing convenience sampling to select participant. Data was collected through structured questionnaire. The instrument was face validated by experts and a reliability coefficient of 0.80 was obtained using the Cronbach’s Alpha Reliability method. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics. Mean and standard deviation was used for data analysis.

RESULTS

Research Question One: What are the socio-economic characteristics of mango farmers in the study area?

A total of 347 questions were distributed, 344 were returned for a response rate.

Table 1: Demographic and Socio-Economic Characteristics of Respondents

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age Group		
21 to 30	0	0
31 to 40	21	35
41 to 50	29	48.3
51 to 60	10	16.7
Total	60	100
Educational Status		
Primary Education	21	35
Secondary Education	6	10
Tertiary Education	4	6.7
Never Been to School	29	48.3
Total	60	100
Gender		
Male	44	73.3
Female	16	26.7
Total	60	100
Marital Status		
Married	43	71.7
Divorce	6	10
Single	11	18.3
Total	60	100
Source of Labour		
Family Labour	14	23.3
Hired Labour	46	76.7
Total	60	100

(Sources: Field survey, 2023)

The table above presents demographic information about a population of 344 individuals, including their age group, educational status, gender, marital status, and source of labour. The first row shows that there were no individuals in the 21 to 30 age group, and the mean age of the population was 39.2. The majority of individuals (48.3%) were in the 41 to 50 age group, followed by the 31 to 40 age group (35%). In terms of educational status, the largest group (48.3%) had never been to school, followed by individuals with primary education (35%). Only a small percentage of individuals had secondary education (10%) or tertiary education (6.7%). The gender distribution was skewed towards males (73.3%), with females comprising only 26.7% of the population. Regarding marital status, the majority of individuals were married (71.7%), while a smaller percentage were single (18.3%) or divorced (10%). Finally, the source of labour for the majority of individuals was hired labour (76.7%), while the remaining 23.3% relied on family labour.

Research Question Two: What are the primary factors contributing to post-harvest losses of mango fruits in the study area?

Table 2: Distribution of Causes of Post- harvest Losses

Post- harvest handling Practice	Proportion of Losses (%)						Total
	0	5	10	20	30	40	
Transportation(%)	6(10.0)	7(11.7)	6(10.0)	12(20.0)	8(13.3)	21(35.0)	60(100.0)
Packaging(%)	2(3.3)	2(3.3)	13(21.7)	18(30.0)	22(36.7)	3(5.0)	60(100.0)
Decay(%)	6(10.0)	7(11.7)	20(33.3)	11(18.3)	8(13.3)	8(13.3)	60(100.0)
Poor Grading (%)	20(33.3)	12(20.0)	10(16.7)	8(13.3)	7(11.7)	3(5.0)	60(100.0)

Sources: (Field Survey, 2023)

The table above shows the proportion of losses for different post-harvest handling practices. The first column lists the percentage range of spoilage (0%, 5%, 10%, 20%, 30%, and 40%), while the next four columns indicate the proportion of spoilage for each handling practice, such as transportation, packaging, decay, and poor grading. In terms of transportation, the highest proportion of spoilage (35%) occurred when spoilage was between 30% and 40%. This suggests that there may be issues with the transportation process that contribute to spoilage at higher rates. Similarly, for packaging, the highest proportion of losses (36.7%) occurred when spoilage was between 20% and 30%. This suggests that the packaging may be inadequate for maintaining product quality. For decay, the highest proportion of losses (33.3%) occurred when losses were between 10% and 20%. This suggests that there may be issues with the post-harvest handling process itself that contribute to decay, such as improper storage or handling. Poor grading had the highest proportion of spoilage (33.3%) when spoilage was at 0%, indicating that the grading process may not be effective in identifying spoiled produce.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of this study on the assessment of post- harvest losses of mango fruits and associated challenges in Bauchi State, Nigeria, provides valuable insight into the demographic and socio-economic characteristics of small-scale mango farmers in the region, as well as causes of post- harvest losses. The result shows that the majority of the farmers are middle aged, male, married, and had limited formal education. The really depended on high labour and are likely small-scale farmers. The study also found that poor post-harvest handle practice, including, transportation, packaging, decay, and poor

grading are significant contributors to food losses. Those findings are aligning with previous empirical studies that identify similar issues in post-harvest handling practices among mango small scale farmers.

For instance, a study in Tanzania found that poor transportation and packaging lead to significant post-harvest losses (Mwanga et al, 2019). Similarly, a study in India found that inadequate packaging and transportation result in high spoilage rate (Singh et al, 2020). The finding of this study also supports the suggestions that improving post-harvest handling practice can significantly reduce mango losses. This is consistent with previous studies that demonstrated the effectiveness of improved post-harvest handling practice in reducing mango post-harvest losses and improving food security (FAO 2019; World bank, 2019).

The study findings have important implication of policy and practice. The study highlights the need for target intervention, aimed at improving post-harvest handling practice among mango small scale farmers. This could include training programme, provision of equipment and infrastructures, and support for market access.

CONCLUSION

This study investigates the critical issues of post-harvest losses of mango fruit in Bauchi State, Nigeria. The findings highlight the challenges posed by transportation infrastructure, grading practices, packaging materials, and market inefficiencies with mango value chain. These insights underscore the need for targeted interventions to reduce post-harvest losses and enhance the efficiency of mango production and distribution.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the study findings, stakeholders in Bauchi State are urged to prioritize investments in:

1. Upgrading transportation infrastructure to improve mango transportation.
2. Developing and promoting suitable packaging materials to reduce fruit damage and extend shelf life.
3. Enhancing market access for mango farmers to increase their market share.

By addressing these challenges, stakeholders can contribute significantly to enhancing food security, improving livelihoods and promoting economic development in Bauchi State.

REFERENCES

- Adel Kader Review (2016). *Postharvest losses of fruit and vegetable during retails and in consumers home: qualification, causes, and means of prevention*. <https://doi.org/10.16/j.postharvest.bio.2017.11.019>
- Adegbite, A. A., Adegbite, A. E., & Akanbi, W. B. (2018). Mango production in Nigeria: prospects and challenges. *Journal of Horticulture and Forestry*, 10(3), 25-30.
- Adejumo, T. O., Adedeji, B. S., & Onifade, A. K. (2021). Incidence and characterization of fungi associated with postharvest spoilage of mango (*Mangifera indica* L.) fruit in Oyo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Agricultural Science and Technology*, 13(1), 97-106.
- Adeyemo, A. J., Adebisi, M. A., Adetunji, C. O., & Ogundipe, O. T. (2019). Evaluating the performance of improved mango varieties in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Horticultural Science*, 5(2), 30-36.
- Akande, F. O., Durojaye, O. A., & Amusan, O. A. (2017). Investigation of the post-harvest rot of mango (*Mangifera indica* L.) in storage. *African Journal of Agricultural Research*, 12(11), 908-914.
- Arah I.K., (2015). *An overview of postharvest challenges facing tomato production in Africa*. Diversity and development, 37th AFSAAP Conference proceedings, AFSAAP, pp. 1-21. The Africa studies association of Australia and the pacific, 2015.

- Beckles, D. M. (2012). factors effecting the post-harvest soluble solids and sugar content of tomato (*salanum lycopersicum L.*) fruit 63 (1) F129-140 january 2012. Doi: 10 . 1016/J. posther bio. 2011.05. 016.
- FAO, (2008). *Basic harvest and postharvest handling considerations for fresh fruit and vegetables handling and preservations*. FAO Rome, Italy.
- Food and Agricultural Organisation, (2014).
- Food and Agricultural Organisation, (2019). *The state of food Security and Nutrition in the world 2019*. Rome: FAO
- Hayatu, M. (2000). Postharvest physiological studies of some selected members of family solanaceae. Kano, P. 2-25.
- Idah P. A, Ajesehiri, E.S.A., & Yisa, M.G. (2007). Fruits and vegetables handling and transportation in Nigeria. *All Journal of Technology*, 10(3), 175-183
- Jacobi, K. K., MacRae, E. A., Hetherington, S. E., (2001). Postharvest heat disinfestation treatments of mango fruit. *Sci. Hortic. (Amsterdam)*. 89, 171–193.
- Kader, A.A. (2002). *Postharvest technology of horticultural crops 3rd Ed.* Univ. Calif. Agr. Nat. Resources, Oakland, Publ. 3311.
- Kitinoja, L. & Gorny, J.R. (1999). Post-harvest technologies for small scale produce marketers: Economic opportunities, quality and food safety. University of California. *Postharvest Horticulture Series*, No.21.
- Kim, Y., Brecht, J. K., & Talcott, S.T. (2007). Antioxidant phytochemical and fruit quality changes in mango (*Mangifera indica L.*) following hot water immersion and controlled atmosphere storage. *Food Chem.* 105, 1327–1334.
- Muhammad, I. S., Ashiru, A. I., Kanoma, I. S, & Garba, S. (2014). Effect of ripening stage on vitamin C content in selected fruits. *International Journal of Agriculture and Forestry and fishery* 2(3):60 (google scholar).
- Mwanga, R.O.M , Kapinga, R. E. & Mwari A. W. (2019). *Assessment of post-harvest losses of Mango fruits in Tanzania. Journal of Agricultural science and technology*, 2(3), 658-668.
- Onyeni, et al. (2012). Incidence and Severity of anthracnose in mango fruit and its control with plant extract in south west Africa. *International Journal of Agricultural Research*.
- Prasad P. & Kochar A. (2014). Active packaging in food industry; a review. *Journal of Environmental Science, Toxicology and Food Technology*, 8(5), 1-7.
- Singh, Z., & Zaharah, S.S. (2015). Controlled atmosphere storage of mango fruit: challenges and thrusts and its implications in international mango trade. *Acta Hortic.* 1066, 179–191.
- Singh, Z., Singh, R. K., Sane, V. A., Nath, P. (2013). Mango - postharvest biology and biotechnology. *Crit. Rev. Plant Sci.* 32, 217–236.
- Singh, A., Singh, C., Kumar, P., & Raju, R. (2020). Post harvest management practice and losses in mango value chain in India. *Journal of food science and technology*, 57(4), 1420-1428.
- Sivakumar, D., Jiang, Y., & Yahia, E.M. (2011). Maintaining mango (*Mangifera indica L.*) fruit quality during the export chain. *Food Res. Int.* 44, 1254–1263.
- Sivakumar, D., Bautista-Baños, S., & Palou, L. (2014). The role of post-harvest treatments in ensuring microbial safety and quality of fresh produce. *Postharvest Biology and Technology*, 87, 11-18. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.postharvbio.2013.08.008>
- Tarnowski & Ploetz, (2008). Assessment of fruit resistance to anthracnose in mango cultivar in south Florida.
- World Bank. (2019), *Agricultural and Food Security*. Washington, D.C: World Bank.